

A Preliminary Study on Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement among Students

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence, which comprises the critical components of intrapersonal and interpersonal connections, flexibility, moods, and stress management, affects students' academic accomplishment. The study tries to find out more about the connection between students' academic success in business management and information technology and their emotional intelligence. Global education has been greatly impacted by the COVID-19 outbreak. When the epidemic initially impacted China, many Chinese towns started to provide online courses. Our objective is to determine how students' emotional intelligence, learning motivation, and self-efficacy impacted negatively academic performance throughout the country. This study examines the relationship between students' self-efficacy and motivation to learn and their academic success. According to the study, there is no connection between pupils' academic success and their emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Academic Performance, Interpersonal Skill.

Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) is defined as the ability to perceive, use, understand, manage and handle emotions. People with high emotional intelligence can recognize their own emotions and those of others, use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour, discern between different feelings and label them appropriately, and adjust emotions to adapt to environments. Although the term first appeared in 1964, it gained popularity in the 1995 best-selling book *Emotional Intelligence*, written by science journalist Daniel Goleman. Goleman defined EI as the array of skills and characteristics that drive leadership performance. Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it is an inborn characteristic.

According to a recent study, emotional intelligence (EI) is associated with more pro-social conduct, improved academic performance, and increased empathy for patients. EI has been related to greater academic performance and stronger doctor-patient relationships in clinical practice and medical school. Interpersonal and intrapersonal relationships, adaptability, moods, and stress management abilities are all essential components of emotional intelligence, and they all have a big impact on a student's academic success. A high

level of emotional intelligence enhances one's ability to build and maintain collaborative relationships, handle stress, and cope to a greater extent with fast change, according to studies published in the *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*.

Emotionally intelligent students are better able to interact with others, do well in educational institutions and at work, and accomplish their personal and professional objectives. Additionally, Emotional intelligence can help students connect with their emotions, put their intentions into practice, and form informed opinions about what is most important to learners. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are better able to grasp the behavioural and psychological health of their students. They may also be more aware of their students' disruptive habits, academic progress, and interpersonal skills.

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a major impact on education. 180 nations or regions have closed schools since the end of April 2020, leaving 85% of youngsters unable to attend (World Bank, 2020a, b). The COVID-19 outbreak presented educators with a classic adaptive and innovative challenge, one to which they had to act swiftly. Consequently, during the epidemic, numerous schools all around the world were able to continue teaching online using their resources (Reimers et al., 2020).

According to Mortiboys (2012), many academics have been interested in how EI affects schooling, and there have been a lot more studies on this subject in recent years (Perera, 2016). According to Mayer et al. (2008), EI has to do with how people control, understand and use their pertinent emotional traits and cognitive skills when interacting with others. EI also means that a person's social intelligence allows them to recognize and distinguish their own and others' emotions to draw accurate conclusions and take appropriate action (Alhebaishi, 2019). For this purpose, this article would like to investigate emotional intelligence, self-awareness, emotional management, empathy and academic performance, self-motivation, and interpersonal skills.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the influence of self-awareness on students' academic performance;
- To examine the influence of self-motivation on students' academic performance;
- To examine the influence of empathy on students' academic performance;
- To examine the influence of emotional management on students' academic performance;
- To examine the influence of interpersonal skills on students' academic performance.

Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Salovey and Mayo were the first to propose the idea of emotional intelligence (EI) (Bar-On, 1997). Individuals with a high level of emotional intelligence (EI) can discriminate between their emotional states as well as those of others, which has the potential to impact their thoughts and behaviours. There are several interconnected cognitive and emotional talents that make up emotional intelligence (Ciarrochi et al., 2001). Self-awareness and self-regulation are also referred to as emotional intelligence (Shafiq and Rana, 2016). To adjust their social conduct, people need to be able to recognize their own and others' emotions

(Mayer and Salovey, 1993). This includes how people alter their feelings and those of others, as well as the emotional content they use while solving problems. Emotion perception encompasses this. Individuals who can recognize, evaluate and manage their own and other students' emotional states to achieve certain goals have a high level of EI (Choudary, 2010). As defined by Mayer et al. (2000), emotional intelligence (EI) is a gestalt made up of many personality traits and talents that enable people to receive and make sense of information that is emotionally charged. In addition, the term zeitgeist meant that individuals throughout human history have been emotionally and rationally integrated. Providing students with the opportunity to learn in an educational setting requires them to acquire academic information as well as social and emotional competencies (Amirian and Behshad, 2016). Study after study has established the importance of emotional intelligence (EI) for academic accomplishment, student learning, and teacher effectiveness (Fallahzadeh).

Self-Awareness and Academic Performance

To be self-conscious is to be aware of the desire to recognize sentiments and how they impact performance. The secret to warning a pupil or anyone about their strength and weakness is this self-awareness. Such students develop self-confidence when they are self-aware or can recognize their abilities. Johnson (2009) claimed that emotional well-being is a crucial component of successful learning. The most important component of students' success is for them to understand how to learn. High academic achievement is demonstrated by students who have the capacity for self-awareness and are intrinsically driven. At the end of the semester or academic year, however, students who lack self-awareness and intrinsic desire are more likely to have low academic standing.

Emotional Management and Academic Performance

In the classroom, self-control of one's cognitive processes as well as one's conduct is an essential component of learning and academic performance. The vast majority, if not all, of students, will eventually become disillusioned and fall short of their academic goals. This is because they rely on their mental and emotional toughness to keep their negative thoughts and feelings in check. Students who can keep their emotions under control will be able to reach their academic potential. MacMullin, C. (1994) supports the premise that competent emotional regulation can increase academic accomplishment. The findings suggest that improved academic accomplishment could be attained by focusing on abilities related to emotion regulation and the ability to cope when confronted with difficult conditions.

Empathy and Academic Performance

Empathy is the ability to care about what your coworker needs. Cooper (2010) said that empathy is the most important thing for gifted children to learn about relationships and success. Most of the time, empathy is shown through facial expressions and body language (Wang, 2014). Pupils do better in school when they can empathize with peers who can read or understand nonverbal cues like voice tone, facial expression, and so on. According to Chow (2006), students' levels of empathy are linked to their academic motivation in a good way, which helps them do better in school.

Self-Motivation and Academic Performance

Interest can be sparked, sustained, and maintained, all of which fall under Bernard's definition of motivation (1965). He asserted that this element of motivation based on students' emotional intelligence is critical if educators hope to inspire them to participate fully in the teaching and learning process and make it enjoyable for them to do so. Self-motivation, on the other hand, is the primary driving force behind this research. Emotional intelligence is a vital factor in increasing students' academic achievement because self-motivation is one of the important elements. In this study, self-motivation refers to pupils who are eager to learn and are aware of their educational goals and objectives to succeed academically. Emotions play a role in one's ability to be self-motivated. Emotions have a direct impact on how a person interacts with others and their environment, and this ultimately influences how they adapt to their surroundings (Kamarudin, 1989). Sikwari (2014) found that academic achievement and self-motivation had a strong link. Students' self-motivation and academic achievement in secondary school mathematics, regardless of gender, are significantly linked. High-motivated pupils tend to do better academically than those who lack drive. (Tella, 2007)

Interpersonal Skills and Academic Performance

Students' social issues and emotional states may be related to their academic achievement, particularly concerning their capacity to employ social skills to gain teachers' help (MacMullin, 1994). Since the social environment in which learning takes place has the power to either encourage or discourage acts that support academic success, interpersonal skills must be cultivated to attain academic success. Students that have trouble interacting with their peers frequently conduct badly, which eventually results in subpar academic performance (Sulzer-Azaraff and Mayer, 1986). According to American psychology professor Stephen N. Elliot's study at Wisconsin University, students who took social skills seminars between 1996 and 1997 displayed improved social skills, which in turn improved their academic performance. His research revealed a link between intellectual achievement and social competence. Johnson (2009) added to this finding by stating that emotional intelligence (like interpersonal skills) enables students to build constructive relationships and have social support, which also helps students perform especially well on exams.

Conclusion

Students start to offer online courses as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The EI of students who take part in online English lessons in this article had no bearing on their academic performance. Student EI has a direct and positive impact on learning motivation and self-efficacy even though it has no direct impact on academic achievement. Higher EI students are more motivated to study and more likely to be affected by others' emotions when taking online courses, which can lower their self-efficacy and, ultimately, their academic performance. They must therefore continue to manage and improve their EI. By offering suitable online coursework, colleges that use online instruction must also prioritize the growth of students' EI. While using online courses, teachers should notice and foster students' learning motivation and self-efficacy since, through these factors, EI can improve

English academic accomplishment. As a result, the relationship between EI and academic success depends heavily on both learning motivation and self-efficacy. Future research on EI and academic success might incorporate the ideas of learning motivation and self-efficacy. According to research, academics are becoming more adept at understanding the complex link between emotional intelligence and academic success.

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